

DYNAMICS AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF 2D MATERIALS

DYNASTY

A COLLABORATIVE PROJECT FOR WIDENING
EXPERIMENTAL NETWORKS AMONG NANOMATERIALS
LABS IN EUROPE, ENABLING LOCAL TEAMS TO PRODUCE
EXCELLENT INTERDISCIPLINARY NANOSCIENCE

ACTIVITIES

- ✓ Development of innovative joint research activities on fine structural and spectroscopic analysis as well as the crystal quality of 2D materials
- ✓ Capability-building function mentoring and intellectual synergies
- ✓ Training on administrative and management issues. Career-oriented training programme. and industry-directed research programme.

GET IN CONTACT

<https://dynasty-project.eu/contact/>

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